

ESTIMATION OF THE LUNAR REGOLITE LAYER USING APOLLO MISSION ACTIVE SYSMIC DATA

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ABSTRACT

Although there has been a huge advance in the progress of lunar research, due to the combination of telescopic, orbital and surface observations, many fundamental scientific questions still need to be answered. Although some hypotheses about the formation and evolution of the Moon are being raised, they still require evidence to be verified, given the little knowledge about the lunar interior and its regolith lining. Important questions to be answered involve the cause of deep earthquakes on the Moon, the size and composition of the lunar nucleus, the stratification (or not) of the lunar mantle and the intense dissipation of seismic waves when propagated by the regolith layer.

One of the technical solutions suggested in the literature for the study of the Moon is the installation of a seismographic network on the surface, in order to monitor its seismic activity, through the seismic experiments of the Apollo missions. The Lunar Seismic Profiling Experiment (LSPE) was one of the experiments resulting from the Apollo 17 mission, launched in December 1972. The purpose of this experiment was to record seismic waves generated by detonations, in addition to monitoring seismic waves generated by natural events. In addition to this, an active seismic experiment, Active Seismic Experiment (ASE), was developed with 3 stations over the years 1969 to 1976.

Within this context, the present project aimed to start studies on the depth of the lunar regolith layer, below the stations, based on the active seismic data collected by the Apollo missions in the ASE and LSPE experiments.